

AN INVESTIGATION OF FACTORS AFFECTING LEARNING MOTIVATION OF BUSINESS ENGLISH MAJORS IN HUFU

Nguyen Thi Mai Huong

Ho Chi Minh University of Food Industry

*Email: huongnguyenthimai@cntp.edu.vn

ABSTRACT

Language acquisition is a long and, sometimes, a tiring process. To overcome difficulties and challenges during their study requires students great effort and hard work which are almost impossible with their strong motivation. In other word, motivation is a deciding factor in English learners' success. Being aware of the vital roles of motivation, English teachers in HUFU have tried their best to inspire their beloved students to have a more satisfying learning and teaching result. However, the achievement has been far from satisfactory. Many students have seemed to lose interest in learning as time goes by, which is very unusual. In order to have deeper insights of factors affecting HUFU English majors' achievement, the researcher of this paper has decided to do an investigation into it. Taking HUFU students' own characteristics and teaching conditions into consideration, the results of this paper are expected to bring about practical solutions that help to promote the effectiveness of English training in HUFU.

Keywords: motivation, learning promotion, demotivating factors, teaching strategy, learning achievement.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is said that language acquisition is a long and, sometimes, a tiring process. To become competent language users, learners need a lot of hard work. They also need to have strong motivation to overcome difficulties before they can achieve their goal. The roles of the success of English learning and teaching have been discussed by many language educators and researchers. It is clear that motivation factors vary by settings, teaching and learning conditions and the subjects involved. Consequently, it is an issue worthy of investigation in any language training institutions.

In Ho Chi Minh University of Food Industry (hereafter called Hufu), the research of motivating factors on English major students are even vitally needed because English has been a new training branch. Although a lot of effort has been made, the learning and teaching results are still far from satisfaction. Many students have seemed to lose interest in learning as time goes by, which leads to their low performance. In order to have a deep insight of key motivational factors influencing HUFU English majors' learning achievement, the researcher of this paper has decided to do an investigation into it. Basing on the findings, some effective ways of fostering these factors are suggested.

Two questions, thus, guide the study:

1. *What motivation factors hinder Hufu English major students' performance?*

2. *What can be done to increase their motivation?*

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 What is motivation?

Although it has been agreed that motivation is something that is directly related with behavior and its crucial values on language acquisition process are undeniable, various definitions have been put forward.

Motivation, as asserted by Gardner (1985, p. 10), is the combination of effort plus desire to achieve the goal of learning the language and favorable attitudes towards learning the language". Sharing his view, Richards et al (1992) also considered motivation as the factors that determine a person's desire to do something.

Harmer (1991) thought motivation came from social psychology and connected closely to students' effort, desire as well as their positive attitudes towards learning.

Oxford and Shearin (1994) defined motivation as a desire to gain an objective, combined with the energy to work towards that objective.

To sum up, despite being explained in different ways by different researchers, it is generally agreed that motivation is a psychological factor that drives language learners internally to overcome all challenges in order to be successful in their learning.

2.2 The role of motivation

Researchers have provided empirical evidences to confirm learners' motivation as an effective device of improving their language acquisition as it determines the extent of active, personal involvement in language learning.

In his research of motivational factors influencing the result of English learners' Bushehr University of Medical Sciences (2011) found out that motivation, as a psychological factor, can impact on English language teaching in EFL classroom in Iran. Based on the results of this research work, the researcher suggests that English teachers, syllabus designers, researchers should pay more attention to motivation as a learning strategy to enhance the effectiveness of their works.

In his language acquisition theory, Krashen (1981) stressed that together with attitudes, motivation is the most influential factor in unconscious language acquisition and the learner's motivational level acts as an affective filter on language intake.

While Carroll (1981) points out in his conscious reinforcement model that language learning begins when learners feels motivated to communicate something to someone, Ellis (1994) asserted that motivation is a potent force in language acquisition.

Reece & Walker (1997 as cited in Gomleksiz 2001) also believe that motivation plays a key role in the second language learning process. They, therefore, believe that a less able student who is highly motivated can achieve greater success than the more intelligent student who is not well motivated. Conversely, without sufficient motivation, even those with the most remarkable abilities cannot accomplish long-term goals, and neither are appropriate curricula and good teaching enough to ensure their achievement.

In a nutshell, all the above-mentioned researchers emphasized the fact that motivation makes purposes clearly visible. Learning a foreign language is very challenging but if learners have

internal desire to learn it, they can do well. Motivation not only increases their interest in learning but also help them to overcome obstacles to achieve the goal. (Gardner, 1985) strongly believes that the motivated person spends effort towards the aim. It is motivation that provides learners with an aim and direction to follow. Without desire, learners can hardly gain effective results. Undoubtedly, to facilitate students' language acquisition process, the teacher's task is to maximize the motivation.

2.3 Research design

Due to limited time and scope of the paper, this study carried out with the deployment of literature review of previous researches, close – talk, discussion with Hufi English major sophomores in 2 classes, in which the researcher is teaching, about their learning problems at school.

3 FACTORS AFFECTING ENGLISH HUFU LEARNERS' MOTIVATION

3.1 Demotivated classmates

Obviously, students' learning attitude can affect their classmate greatly. Students with low motivation do not concentrate well in class and do not well co-operate with their partners to do assigned tasks in pairs or groups. This behavior certainly lowers their peers' motivation. Low motivation learners are usually inattentive in class, which distracts their classmates' attention greatly. A discussion in groups of 5 - 7 students about their learning difficulties also reveals that their peer's uncooperative attitude and laziness usually make them less motivated, especially the expected noise they make in class, their personal conversation really annoy those who want to listen to the lecture. Consequently, their learning motivation is negatively impacted.

3.2 Unfavorable learning environment

MacIntyre (1999) put it that a safe classroom climate can help to motivate learners because they would feel comfortable to learn a language in this idea condition. Sharing his view, Good and Brophy (1994) also asserted that effective language learning occurs in a relaxed and friendly class. They go on further confirming that motivation cannot be developed in a difficult classroom and teachers should be responsible for creating an effective learning environment for their learners.

Group discussion and close talks with students point out that they often feel stressed or very unsafe and not self – confident to present their ideas in the class because of their limited language proficiency. Consequently, they rarely dare to stand up and share their views with their classmates and their teachers. They prefer to talk to the teachers so that their mistakes can be corrected personally without making them embarrassed.

A sudden change in the learning environment was also stated by the target students as a challenge for them because they have to spend of their time self-studying. Meanwhile, they were taught everything necessary by their teachers at high school. Besides, many of the students thought that the atmosphere in the class room is strict. They preferred a more supportive and friendly one.

3.3 Language level

Obviously, language competence is a key factor which affects learners' motivation. If the input language input is difficult, they can not fully comprehend. Consequently, they may lack a confidence in their ability and their chance to be successful. To make the matter worse, many students may lose their heart and they do not want to try any more. Most Hufi English majors come

from the countryside, thus, many of them do not have good English knowledge. Unsurprisingly, they mention all kind of typical problems for learners of this level: poor pronunciation, limited vocabulary and structure to express their ideas in productive skills. Even receptive skills also cause them great difficulties in understanding. Some of them even doubt if they are able to acquire English successfully.

3.4 Teachers

The importance of teacher factors in students' learning motivation and achievement is unarguable. It is generally agreed that motivation also depends on the social interaction between the teacher and the learner. According to Cooper & McIntyre (1998 as cited in Gomleksiz 2001), the more effective the teacher will facilitate more productive learning. The choice of a teaching strategy, undoubtedly, will have an effect upon the motivation and interest of the learners. The manner in which the teacher approaches a teaching strategy will have an effect upon motivation: an enthusiastic approach is more likely to motivate than a dull one. To be able to create an effective learning environment and to motivate students, strong interpersonal and social interaction is needed. Appropriate forms of interaction help students deal with their problems in the learning process.

Although great effort has been extended by English teachers in Hufi, their time in classroom is limited. Therefore, they devote most of their time teaching to catch up the schedule. Consequently, a number of students questioned agreed that their teachers were friendly, enthusiastic and highly qualified they still feel a big distance to express their view, especially when they need their teachers' help.

4 SOME PRELIMINARY SUGGESTIONS

As learning a language is a long and tiring process which needs a lot of time, energy and effort. Consequently, keeping students motivated is vital for the success. Basing on the results discussed above, some suggestions are made as below:

First, teachers can help to minimize students' negative effect on their peers in the class by making them follow the class rules strictly. Besides, group study should be encouraged so that students with poor English proficiency can get needed help from their partners. Pair and Group Activities should be assigned frequently to develop students' confidence and sense of responsibility for their own learning.

Second, a friendly atmosphere in the classroom should be created as this helps students feel more comfortable and safe participating in classroom activities after they know their teacher and their peers. A low-anxiety learning environment has a great impact on language acquisition as it increases their desire to learn and develop their language skills as they have no fear of embarrassment when they make mistakes.

Last but not least, supplementary courses should be provided to students to compensate the knowledge and skills they lack so that they can catch up with the requirement of Hufi training program.

5 CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Obviously, teachers cannot effectively teach English if they do not fully understand factors that hinder their students' motive of learning as well as their effects on language acquisition. This study, therefore, has been done with an aim to find out psychological reasons that English major students

in Hufi are facing and some solutions to these problems. Due to limited time, only four motivating reasons have been discussed namely demotivated classmates, unfavorable learning environment, language level and teacher factor. Basing on the finding, some suggestions have also been made with the hope to increase the effectiveness of learning and teaching English to majors in Hufi.

Limitations

There were some imitations or shortcomings in this study. First of all, the researcher finished the study in a short time. Only one week for conduction the group discussion and close talk with students was not enough. Secondly, the number of the population was only restricted to the students in her class; this is a very small group of population for research. However, the finding is expected to lay a foundation to deeper and more extensive researches about this topic in Hufi in the near future.

REFERENCE

- [1] Al-Otaibi, G. (2004). Language Learning Strategy Use among Saudi EFL Students and Its Relationship to Language Proficiency Level, Gender, and Motivation [PhD Dissertation].
- [2] Broussard, S. C., & Garrison, M. E. B. (2004). The Relationship between Classroom Motivation and Academic Achievement in Elementary School-aged Children. *Family and Consumer Sciences Research Journal*, 33(2), 106–120.
- [3] Brown, H. D. (2000). *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching*. (4th ed.). New York
- [4] Chalak, A. & Kassaian, Z.(2010).Motivation And Attitudes Of Iranian Undergraduate EFL Students Towards Learning English. *GEMA Online™ Journal of Language Studies* 37 Volume 10(2)2010. ISSN: 1675-8021.
- [5] Dital, R. C. (2012). The Motivation for and Attitude towards Learning English. *Asian EFL Journal*, 63. Dornyei, Z. (1996).
- [6] Dörnyei, Z. (2001a). *Motivational strategies in the language classroom*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- [7] Dörnyei, Z. (2001b). *Teaching and researching motivation*. Harlow: Longman.
- [8] Edward Arnold Ltd, London, Great Britain. Gardner, R. C., & Lambert, W. (1972). *Attitudes and Motivation in Second Language Learning*.
- [9] Gardner, R. C. (1985). *Social psychology and second language learning: The role of attitudes and motivation*. London: Edward Arnold Publishers.
- [10] Krashen, Stephen D(1987). *Principles and Practice in Second Language Acquisition*. Prentice-Hall International.
- [11] Oxford and Shearin (1994) *Language Learning Motivation: Expanding the Theoretical Framework*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.1994.tb02011.x>
- [12] Sadighi, F., & Maghsudi, N. (2000). The Relationship between Motivation and English Proficiency among Iranian EFL Learners. *Indian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 26(1), 39-52.